

Applying a Task-Based Approach to Distributed Machine Learning Workflows

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I. ARTIFACT DESCRIPTION

In order to facilitate the reproducibility of the experiments contained in this article we uploaded to a public repository the scripts with the code used in the experiments. The public repository is a GitHub project and its link is: https://github.com/lezzidan/aisprint_dislib. The repository contains also the launching scripts used in MareNostrum4 and Power-9. The unique requirement to reproduce correctly the experiments is to adjust the number of nodes desired to use.

In the repository there is a folder which contains the scripts of the Neural Networks, both the nesting and the normal execution together with the corresponding launching scripts.

This repository is still alive, and their scripts may suffer changes from the versions used in this article. For this reason we made a release in GitHub and created a tag with the correct version of the codes. The release is in: https://github.com/lezzidan/aisprint_dislib/releases/tag/v1.0

The dataset used in the experiments can be downloaded from B2Drop, using the following URL: <https://b2drop.bsc.es/index.php/s/8Q8MefXX2rrzaWs>.

Using the data contained on this repository together with the scripts in the GitHub the tests can be easily reproduced on a supercomputer or cluster where dislib, EDDL and PyCOMPSs are installed. A docker container using the Dockerfile contained in the GitHub repository can be generated in order to execute the tests without the need of installing PyCOMPSs, dislib neither EDDL.

An execution of each of the machine learning algorithms were documented using provenance. The information of the executions obtained using provenance was uploaded to workflowhub in order to ensure the reproducibility and register the details of the executions. The CascadeSVM information execution is on <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/1124>, the execution of kNN is on <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/1123> and the Random Forest information execution on <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/1122>.

We also uploaded some scripts to Zenodo and we created a DOI with the executed code. The links to the Neural Network scripts in Zenodo are: <https://zenodo.org/records/8093848> and <https://zenodo.org/records/8093544>. We registered the logs of various executions of the kNN algorithm, which are uploaded

to Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/7426459>, in this repository we also included the traces of the executions. Finally, in <https://zenodo.org/records/5734309> we uploaded another script with the whole execution of the workflow, it contains the preprocessing of the dataset, the training of the algorithm and the score obtained in the validation data.